

ENTREPRENEURIAL PASSION AND PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN ENUGU STATE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15026096>

Abstract: *The study evaluated the entrepreneurial passion and performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between entrepreneurial creativity and revenue generation and evaluate the relationship between entrepreneurial commitment and sales volumes of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 293 entrepreneurs was used. Two hundred and fifty-five (255) returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Z - test. The findings indicated that i. Entrepreneurial Creativity had significant positive relationship with the revenue generation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), $Z(95, n = 255), 6.391 < 9.331, P. <.05$ and Entrepreneurial Commitment had positive significant relationship with the sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), $Z(95, n = 255), 6.888 < 9.159, P. <.05$. The study concluded that Entrepreneurial Creativity and commitment had significant positive relationship with the revenue generation and Sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The study recommended among others that the management of the small and medium enterprises should be encouraged to be creative to help builds confidence and teach valuable life skills, including cognitive, physical and social emotional skills.*

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial passion, Performance, Entrepreneurial creativity, Revenue generation, Entrepreneurial commitment & Sales volume.*

1.1 Introduction

The number one challenge of all Entrepreneurs is that we want to do every single thing in the business ourselves. As an Entrepreneur, I wanted to do everything myself. A good team and system in place mean that the business will continue to run consistently even when you are away from the business. A

Innovative Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business (IJEB)

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836-3960

Impact Factor: 9.68

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJEB/index>,

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

good system in place means that the System is the boss of the entire team and you included. So the System is the boss of the team and you, the system pushes you and the team forward consistently every day (Lim, 2024). But, with the rapid advancement of technology, an evolving work culture and increased access to capital for entrepreneurs of all types, entrepreneurship is an appealing career choice for many. Simply put, entrepreneurship is the act of starting a business with the intention of turning a profit. However, the modern definition of entrepreneurship has expanded to include the act of transforming the world by solving large-scale problems. With the advent of the internet, entrepreneurship has the power to create social change through the creation of a service or product that affects individuals in positive ways and addresses social issues with innovative ideas, (Ownr, 2024). The most important thing is to be passionate about what you do and always give it the best you have. This is the key to success. Passion provides us with the energy to go toward our dreams. It is the Motivation or desire to do something and also psychological force to do something. Passion is the key of staying inspired and pushing ourselves to do the best work. Without passion, hard work can often feel tedious and uninspiring. Finding what you are passionate about is essential to achieving success. We must be able to identify the things that we are truly passionate about to make our dreams a reality. Entrepreneurial passion is a motivational attitude characterized by positive emotional arousal, internal drive, and engagement with meaningful work that is significant to an entrepreneur's self-identity. It is essential for success of entrepreneurial projects and differentiates between the success and failure of an entrepreneur. To succeed, every entrepreneur must have a passion that drives him/her forward, that is, a strong belief that keeps him/her pressing on even if others don't have the same vision. Think for a moment about your true passion and what makes you happy about the work you do. Those who do so are more bound to succeed in their business than those who do not, (Bizmanualz, 2022). Passion is innate and cannot be learned or acquired. It powers the hard work, determination, and creativity to reach goals and attain significant accomplishments possible. All successful people, including athletes, scientists, novelists, and others who have risen to the top of their fields, all had a passion for what they were doing, (Bizmanualz, 2022). Performance refers to the speed at which an application functions. It is a multifaceted aspect of quality. When we are talking about web applications, the time it takes your application to be presented to your users is what we will call web performance. The speed at which your application responds to your users' interactions is what we will call runtime performance. These are the two facets of performance that we will be looking at, (Barker, 2012). Performance is seen as the vital result anticipated in all business activity (Muhammad et al., 2019) (Ahmed, Shah, Qureshi, Shah & Khuwaja, 2018), (Galdeano, Ahmed, Fati, Rehan & Ahmed, 2019), performance refers to a company's overall performance as measured by the sum of its financial, marketing, and human resource operations over a period of time. Firms set goals and objectives that must be met within a certain time limit. The efficacy of an organization is

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measured by how well it achieves its goals. Thus, organizational performance refers to an organization's capacity to meet its objectives, such as a high profit margin, high product quality, a higher market share, and improved financial outcomes, within a given time frame and by implementing the appropriate strategy (Olusegun, Olympus, & Olakunle, 2020). Performance is defined as the accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed. In a contract, performance is deemed to be the fulfillment of an obligation, in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract (McNamara, 2018). It is the completion of a task with application of knowledge, skills and abilities. In the work place, performance or job performance means good ranking with the hypothesized conception of requirements of a task role, whereas citizenship performance means a set of individual activity/contribution (pro-social organizational behaviour) that supports the organizational culture. Performance is the outcome of the various activities undertaken by the organization, a reflection of the way in which tangible and intangible resources are invested in the organization in order to achieve the desired goals and performance, as McNamara (2018). Based on this, the study aimed at evaluating Entrepreneurship passion and performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state.

Statement of the problem

Entrepreneurial passion is consciously accessible, intense positive feelings experienced by engagement in entrepreneurial activities associated with roles that are meaningful and salient to the self-identity of the entrepreneur. Since it is associated with positive feelings and attitudes toward activities that are central to people's lives, it makes some entrepreneurs persist in their venture efforts and drive their success. Passion gives the motivation and confidence that one need to deliver the mission and purpose for what you do and why you do it. Passion helps you network with the right people who share similar perspectives As a result of the development and progress of economic globalization, more and more people choose to start their own businesses under strong national and governmental supports, which not only promote the economic development of the country, but also alleviate the employment situation to a certain extent but lack of strong will to take risks, lack of effective communication, insufficient ability and knowledge in starting and running a business effectively and lack of entrepreneurship skills in the inability to identify and seize business opportunities have become a bottleneck for the entrepreneurs. Also, lack of creativity, commitment, flexibility, dedication, passion, self-confidence and above all, leadership has contributed negatively for entrepreneur's success.

The consequences of the above if not tackled will lead to poor revenue generation and poor sales volume. Stress, overestimating strengths, and making poor strategic choices. Based on this, the study aimed at entrepreneurial passion and performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the entrepreneurial passion and performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between entrepreneurial creativity and revenue generation of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between entrepreneurial commitment and sales volumes of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state

1.3 Research Question

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the relationship between entrepreneurial creativity and revenue generation of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state
- ii. What is the relationship between entrepreneurial commitment and sales volume of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state

1.4 Statement of Hypotheses

- i. Entrepreneurial creativity has relationship with the revenue generation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs)
- ii. Entrepreneurial commitment has relationship with the sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Entrepreneurial

Entrepreneurial skills encompass several key areas including leadership, direction, coordinating, oversight, planning and organization. Within these key areas, Entrepreneurial skills combine hard and soft skills that professionals in management roles must have to succeed in their careers. Essentially, effective managerial skills comprise traits that supervisors and leaders apply to motivate and direct staff, manage production and financial processes and schedule and organize workflow. Also, many managers and leaders take part in continuous professional development to perform their jobs successfully (Indeed Editorial Team, 2022). The role of managerial skill in the survival of organization cannot be overemphasized, because equipment and money on their own cannot reproduce themselves or make profit without human efforts (Orji, Akhimien & Egwuatu, 2023).

2.1.2 Passion

A passion is a value that holds significant meaning to you or an activity that you enjoy doing. When you practice your passions, you might feel content and relaxed. As a professional, pursuing your passions as a career can bring you greater fulfillment in the contributions you make in the workplace. You might also prefer to exercise your hobbies outside of the work environment, where being passionate can help you develop and maintain a healthy work-life balance, (Birt, 2023).

2.1.3 Entrepreneurial Passion

Entrepreneurial passion is experienced through strong emotions and motivations that are intertwined closely with an individual's entrepreneurial identity. Entrepreneurial passion originates from engagement with self-defining activities over time; entrepreneurs are not born with passion, they develop it. The emerging research surrounding entrepreneurial passion indicates it can have powerful effects, both positive and negative. Regarding the positive, entrepreneurial passion drives beneficial cognitive and behavioral outcomes such as creativity, commitment, and effort. Regarding the negative, entrepreneurial passion can also drive rigidity and burnout. Moreover, research shows that entrepreneurial passion can be contagious; it has the power to infuse stakeholders surrounding entrepreneurs and attract new venture investors to provide early-stage funding, (Murnieks and Cardon, 2023).

2.1.4 Components of Entrepreneurial Passion

According to Murnieks and Cardon (2023), the noted that regarding the positive, entrepreneurial passion include: creativity, commitment, and effort. Byjus (2021), maintained that the components of entrepreneurial passion include: organization, Innovation and vision risk.

Components of Entrepreneurial Passion that formed part of the study

2.1.4.1 Creativity

Creativity is the ability to make or otherwise bring into existence something new, whether a new solution to a problem, a new method or device, or a new artistic object or form (Kerr, 2022). It is also a phenomenon whereby something new and valuable is formed Creativity is defined as the tendency to generate or recognize ideas, alternatives, or possibilities that may be useful in solving problems, communicating with others, and entertaining ourselves and others. A creative workplace gives employees the ability to come up with unique solutions to challenges instead of simply being told what to do. Many employees will gladly offer up ideas to improve processes and help make the business more efficient if they are given the option. Creative individuals seem to have a need to seek novelty and an ability to pose unique questions. When creative persons find a better solution, they then work toward "selling" others on the concept (Kerr, 2022).

2.1.4.2 Commitment

Entrepreneurial commitment refers to the level of engagement and dedication team members feel toward their individual jobs and the organization. It also describes the different reasons professionals remain with an employer rather than seek opportunities elsewhere. High levels of commitment can increase workplace productivity, bolster team morale and enhance a company's ability to reach its objectives. Whether you're a team lead or a team member, knowing how to create an organizational culture that emphasizes commitment can help increase your ability to deliver results and achieve goals, (Indeed, 2023).

2.1.5 Performance

Organizational performance is an indicator of the level of achievement that can be achieved and reflects the success of an organization, as well as the results achieved from the behavior of organizational members (Supriadi, Guswandi and Saragih, 2020). Performance can also be said as a result (output) of a particular process carried out by all components of the organization against certain sources used (input). The performance of an organization depends on the individual work performance of employees.

2.1.6 Components of performance

According to some authors (Verboncu & Zalman, 2005) performance is "a particular result obtained in management, economics, marketing, etc. that print features of competitiveness, efficiency and effectiveness of the organization and its procedural and structural components. can be seen as the effective accomplishment of tasks, leading to the achievement of specific goals and objectives. Performance is often measured against predetermined standards of accuracy, revenue generation, completeness, Sales volume, profitability, cost, and speed (Elger, 2014) maintained that Cost decreases, Capability increases, Capacity increases, Knowledge increases, Skills increase and Identity and motivation increases, output, and revenue generation.

2.1.7 Components of performance that formed part of the study

2.1.6.1 Revenue generation

The essence of revenue generation is to advance the welfare of citizens of a country with focus on promoting economic growth and development through the provision of development activities. Despite remarkable growth recorded in revenue generation the physical state of the nation in terms of social amenities and infrastructure remain backward (Ogbeifun Ajetunmobi, Moronkeji and Adindu, 2019). The rationale for revenue generation in markets economy such as Nigeria stems from the government responsibilities, which include but are not restricted to stabilization of the economy, redistribution of income and provision of services in the form of public goods.

2.1.6.2 Sales volume

Sales volume is the quantity or number of goods sold or services sold in the normal operations of a company in a specified period (Business Dictionary, 2020). Sales volume measures how many units of a product your company sells during a specific reporting period. On its own, sales volume doesn't break down how much revenue your company is bringing in from product sales. However, understanding your sales volume can tell you what products are and aren't selling, which is valuable information for business growth (Alfred, 2020).

2.1.7 Conceptual model of the study

Fig: 2.1 Conceptual model of the study

Source: Author’s Model, 2024

The diagram above shows the linkages between the various components of Entrepreneurial Passion and performance. The aim of the diagram is to show how improvements in these Entrepreneurial Passion components and variables translate into improvements in the organizational performance of the selected SMEs. The diagram shows that comfort talking has a high chance of improving the revenue generation of the SMEs, thereby increasing productivity ratios and entrepreneurial commitment on fulfilling the needs within the organization will lead to greater sales volume of the SMEs. The end product of these will culminate in the improved organizational productivity.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The following theories guided the study

2.2.1 Dynamic Capabilities Theory

Dynamic Capabilities Theory, introduced by David Teece in 1997

Moreover, Dynamic Capabilities Theory posits that firms can cultivate and enhance their dynamic capabilities through various mechanisms, including organizational learning, experimentation, and strategic adaptation. Organizational learning entails the acquisition, assimilation, and exploitation of new knowledge and insights derived from both internal and external sources. Experimentation involves taking calculated risks and exploring novel approaches to problem-solving and value creation. Strategic adaptation encompasses the ability to flexibly adjust organizational structures, processes, and routines in response to changing market dynamics and competitive pressures (Teece, 2007). Overall, Dynamic Capabilities Theory provides a robust framework for understanding how firms can proactively respond to changing environments and drive sustainable growth through dynamic adaptation and innovation. By embracing the principles of Dynamic Capabilities Theory, pharmaceutical manufacturing firms can position themselves to thrive in today's digital age and emerge as leaders in their respective markets

2.2.2 Theory of Organizational Creativity

The study was anchored on theory of organizational creativity developed by Woodman, Sawyer and Griffin in the year 1993. The theory posits that A creative situation is, therefore, the “sum total of social and environmental (contextual) influences on creative behavior. The theory of organizational creativity was developed by Woodman, Sawyer, and Griffin (1993). They define organizational creativity as “the creation of a valuable, useful new product, service, idea, procedure, or process by individuals working together in a complex social system”. According to this theory, organizational creativity provides a key to the understanding of organizational effectiveness and survival. It is a function of individual characteristics, group characteristics, and organizational characteristics.

Individual characteristics consist of cognitive abilities, personality, intrinsic motivation, and knowledge. Group characteristics consist of norms, cohesiveness, size, diversity, roles, task and problem-solving approaches. Organizational characteristics consist of culture, resources, rewards, strategy, structure, and technology.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Creativity and Revenue generation

Halilu, Mohd and Muhammad (2017) Empirical Investigation on the Relationship between Strategic Orientations and SMEs Performance in Nigeria. This study examines the relationship between strategic orientations and SMEs performance in Nigeria. The debate on entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation to firm performance will for a long time remain area of research. The population of this paper consists of 3,723 of all the SMEs operating in Kaduna and Sokoto state North West Nigeria. Out of which 351 sample questionnaires were administered to respondents concerning the entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation to SMEs performance. 218 questionnaires were returned. The number of valid questionnaires is 213. The data were analyzed using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) to determine the effect of the variables of the study. The findings of the paper indicated that entrepreneurial orientation promoting SMEs performance in Kaduna and Sokoto state North West Nigeria. Similarly, the result shows a statistically significant positive influence of entrepreneurial orientation to SMEs performance. While market orientation has no relationship with SMEs' performance in Kaduna and Sokoto state North West Nigeria. The findings will provide the government, policy maker(s) and other SMEs' stakeholders with the important variables of these entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation to SMEs performance in Nigeria. Implications and Suggestions for future research direction were discussed Okoli, Nwosu & Okechukwu (2021). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Performance of Selected SMEs in Southeast, Nigeria. This study examines the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on performance of selected small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Southeast Nigeria. The problems that led to this study include, inadequate access to finance, poor infrastructure, inconsistency with government policy, poor support (business development work), inadequate sales, too many taxes and obsolete technologies leading to massive failures. It has not been found that the epileptic growth of SMEs in Southeast Nigeria is not only due to the problems but also from the entrepreneurial orientation. The survey research method was employed in this study and the study relied on secondary and primary data. The population of this study was drawn from SMEs in the five states in the Southeast Nigeria. The study was done using three hundred and sixty six small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Complete enumeration was adopted. Simple regression analysis was used to analysis the hypotheses. The study revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between pro-activeness, innovativeness and risk taking on performance of SMEs in Southeast Nigeria. The study concluded that entrepreneurial-oriented firms tend to lead the industry with innovations, performing things in a better approach to satisfy customers and give the firm a better leverage. The study recommends that SMEs owners and managers should be committed to process and radical innovation in their dealings so as to increase and expand their customer

base.Owulo, Okeke & Akaegbobi (2021) Dynamic Capability and Sustainability of SMEs. Dynamic capability (DC) is an ability that has helped big corporations navigate successfully through the ever-changing and competitive business environment. However, SMEs in the southeast of Nigeria seem not to have fully maximized the opportunities embedded in these practices, hence, the need to examine the dynamic capabilities SMEs in Southeast Nigeria need, to stay relevant and ahead of competitors. This study, therefore, looked at the concept of DC and those capabilities that could help SMEs stay afloat in the ever-changing business environment. The capabilities looked at include sensing, absorptive and adaptive capabilities. Others are innovative networking and integrative capabilities. The study further examined the micro-foundations of DC and the composition of SMEs in South East, Nigeria. To embellish the work, Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) was used to anchor the work. Some studies were reviewed empirically. The study concluded that DC is one of the surest ways to ensure that SMEs compete favourably in the ever dynamic marketplace. Hence, it was recommended among other things that SMEs need not to be operating in isolation of what is happening in the global market, as what happens outside has an implication on what happens inside the organization, and as such, need to be alert through the application of DC principles. Lyndon and Opinion (2021). An Evaluation of the Impact of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMES) Development on Economic Growth in Nigeria. This study evaluated the impact of small and medium enterprises development on economic growth in Nigeria. The study used aggregate asset base and aggregate capitalization of SMEs as the independent variables, while gross domestic product (proxy for economic growth) was adopted as the dependent variable. Secondary time series data were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin 2018, National Bureau of Statistics 2018, and National Survey of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) 2013 & 2017 conducted by the Small & Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) for the period 2000 to 2018. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis based on the OLS technique (with the aid of SPSS version 19) were employed as methods for data analysis. The findings show that the aggregate asset base and aggregate capitalization of SMEs have little or no significant effect on the GDP. It was also discovered that there exists a long-run relationship among the variables even though the overall regression model was not statistically significant at 5%. It was recommended amongst others that more efforts should be put in place by Government to gather enough information on SMEs through the responsible. The Federal and /State Ministries of Industry in collaboration with SMEDAN should work out strategies for reporting the operations of SMEs in Nigeria, highlighting the asset base and aggregate capitalization of the sector and put in places policies to resuscitate the sector.

2.3.2 Entrepreneurial Commitment and sales volume

Anoke, Onu & Agagbo (2022) conducted a study on the effect of managerial competencies on the growth of SMEs in Abuja Metropolis, Nigeria. The study adopted Raosoft to determine a sample size of 395. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection, while regression was used for data analysis. It was found that both technical and personal competencies have a positive and strong effect on the growth of SMEs, while conceptual skills recorded a negative and insignificant effect on the growth of SMEs in the Abuja Metropolis. This study is limited to SMEs operators in Abuja Metropolis (the political capital of Nigeria), Leaving Lagos (the economic capital of Nigeria untouched). It is only

when Lagos is covered that one can give a clear direction if Nigerian SMEs operators are changing with the changing business world. Operators, owners as well as policymakers in SMEs are expected to benefit from this study as it will serve as an eye-opener to the hidden and untapped potentials embedded in the proper application of managerial skills. Njoku, Ukaoha, Anthony, Ajibare & Oluleye (2022) conducted a study on the Assessment of Investment Decisions and Financial Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in the Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted and used. Data were collected through the use of structured questionnaires from 400 sampled SMEs. Data were analyzed using, Descriptive Statistics, Correlation Matrix and Logit Regression Model. The results show there is a positive correlation between annual return i.e. financial performance and new property acquisition and a negative correlation existed with new plant and acquisition. The result of the logit model shows that the factors influencing investment decisions among SMEs were the coefficient of education ($P < 0.01$) probability level. The coefficient of the competition level was negative and statistically significant at ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, the coefficient of the initial investment capital ($P < 0.05$). The coefficient of the infrastructure was positive and statistically significant at ($P < 0.05$). Odokoro, Uzuagu & Abanyam (2022) conducted a study on cooperate social responsibility and environmental sustainability strategies among SMEs in Enugu State. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study was seventy-eight (78). Validated questionnaire was used for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were utilized for analyzing research question while ANOVA was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that the strategies used by SMEs in implementing CSR in Enugu State included ensuring safety of employees, adequate waste disposal management and prevention of waste pollutants to host communities. Findings also indicated that the strategies used by SMEs in implementing ES included ensuring that the business activities do not affect the natural environment, reducing pollutants in the environment, implementing green manufacturing practices such as waste reduction, reuse and recycling, among others. ANOVA showed that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of SMEs on the strategies used in implementing environmental sustainability. Among recommendations made was that SMEs should engage in recycling of wastes from their activities. Orga, Aniezue, Unaogu, Emehelu, Ugwa & Udeagha (2023) conducted a study on the relationship between Entrepreneurship education and Performance of the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to: Examine the relationship between training workshops and problem solving skills; evaluate the relationship between mentorship and reduction of unemployment and ascertain the relationship between opportunity evaluation and the number of business start-ups by SMEs in Enugu State. The area of the study comprised staff SMEs in Enugu State metropolis. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. A total population of three hundred and twenty (320), staff was used. The whole population was used due to small size. Two hundred and eighty two (282) staff returned the questionnaire accurately filled. Data were presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistical tool. The findings indicated that training workshops had direct positive relationship with problem solving skills, $r(95, n = 282) = .484 < .782, p < 0.05$; mentorship had direct positive relationship with the reduction of

unemployment $r(95, n = 282) = .511 < .730, p < 0.05$. And opportunity evaluation had direct positive relationship with the number of business startups by SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria $r(95, n = 282) = .515 < .760, p < 0.05$. Nwabueze, Orga and Egbo (2023) conducted a study on the Effect of Authority Dimension on Leadership performance of SMEs in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of Founder authority on the development of SMES in Enugu State and evaluate the effect of Relational authority on the accomplishment of tasks of SMEs in Enugu State. The population of the study was five (5) selected small and Median Enterprises (SMEs) with three hundred and twenty-two (322) staff in Enugu State. The whole population was used due to small number. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. 294 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data from the questionnaire was administered and analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation, and the research hypotheses were tested using Z – test. The findings indicated that Founder authority had significance positive effect on the development of SMEs in Enugu State, $Z(95, n= 294) = 5.861 < 8.369, P<0.05$. Relational authority had significant positive effect on the accomplishment of tasks of SMEs in Enugu state, $Z(95, n= 294) = 5.230 < 11.664, P<0.05$. The study concluded that Founder authority and Relational authority had significant positive effect on development and accomplishment of tasks of SMEs in Enugu state.

2.4 Summary of Empirical Review

Table 2.4.1 shows the Summary of Empirical Review

S/ N	Author(s)	Year	Location	Topic	Methodology	Findings
2	Anoke, Onu & Agagbo	2022	Abuja Metropolis, Nigeria	Managerial Competencies and Growth of Small and Medium Enterprise (SMEs) in Abuja Metropolis, Nigeria	Regression	It was found that both technical and personal competencies have a positive and strong effect on the growth of SMEs, while conceptual skills recorded a negative and insignificant effect on the growth of SMEs in the Abuja Metropolis.
4	Njoku, Ukaoha, Anthony, Ajibare & Oluleye	2022	Nigeria	Assessment Of Investment Decisions And Financial Performance Of Small And Medium Enterprises In Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria	Descriptive Statistics, Correlation Matrix and Logit Regression Model	The results show there is a positive correlation between annual return i.e. financial performance and new property acquisition and a negative correlation existed with new plant and acquisition. The result of the logit model shows that the factors influencing investment decisions among SMEs were the coefficient of education ($P<0.01$) probability level. The coefficient of the competition level was negative and statistically significant at ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, the coefficient of the initial investment capital ($P<0.05$). The coefficient of the infrastructure

						was positive and statistically significant at ($P < 0.05$).
5	Odokoro, Uzuagu & Abanyam	2022	Enugu State	Strategies Adopted by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMES) in Implementing Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Sustainability in Enugu State		Findings revealed that the strategies used by SMEs in implementing CSR in Enugu State included ensuring safety of employees, adequate waste disposal management and prevention of waste pollutants to host communities. Findings also indicated that the strategies used by SMEs in implementing ES included ensuring that the business activities do not affect the natural environment, reducing pollutants in the environment, implementing green manufacturing practices such as waste reduction, reuse and recycling, among others.
7	Orga, Aniezue, Unaogu, Emehelu, Ugwa & Udeagha	2023	Enugu State	Entrepreneurship Education And Performance Of Small And Medium Enterprises (SMEs) In Enugu State	Pearson correlation coefficient (r)	The findings indicated that training workshops had direct positive relationship with problem solving skills, $r(95, n = 282) = .484 < .782, p < 0.05$; mentorship had direct positive relationship with the reduction of unemployment $r(95, n = 282) = .511 < .730, p < 0.05$. And opportunity evaluation had direct positive relationship with the number of business startups by SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria $r(95, n = 282) = .515 < .760, p < 0.05$.
9	Nwabueze, Orga and Egbo	2023	Enugu State	Effect Of Authority Dimension On Leadership Performance Of Median Enterprises (Smes) In Enugu State (SMES) In Enugu State	Z – test	The findings indicated that Founder authority had significance positive effect on the development of SMEs in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 294) = 5.861 < 8.369, P < 0.05$. Relational authority had significant positive effect on the accomplishment of tasks of SMEs in Enugu state, $Z(95, n = 294) = 5.230 < 11.664, P < 0.05$.

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2024

2.5 Gap in Empirical Literature

The studies done were carried outside entrepreneurial passion and performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the Entrepreneurial Creativity and revenue generation, Entrepreneurial commitment and Sales volume of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the entrepreneurial passion and performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state.

Methodology

3.1 Research Design

A research design is the study's structure or strategy that guides data collection and analysis. The survey research approach was used for this investigation. The study used a descriptive survey research design since it included assessing phenomena without attempting to manipulate the study variables and is distinguished by the use of random samples from the public to gather empirical information of modern nature.

3.2 Area of the Study

The area of study was Enugu State, Nigeria

3.3 Sources of Data

Sources of data collection included primary and secondary sources.

3.3.1 Primary Sources

Primary data refer to original data collected basically for the purpose of the study. Questionnaire was adopted for collection of primary data.

3.3.2 Secondary Sources

Secondary data were obtained from facts already documented by others which are considered valid for the study. The secondary source of data for this study includes textbooks, internet, journals, articles and unpublished works.

3.4 Population of the Study

The population of the study was One thousand, six hundred and sixty three (1263) registered members of SMEs in Enugu State.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

The study applied Freund and William's statistic formula, as cited by Freund and William, to determine the appropriate sample size (Uzoagulu, 2011).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 N(pq)}{N(e)^2 + Z^2 (pq)}$$

Where n = Sample Size

N = the population

p = Probability of success/proportion

q = Probability of failure/proportion

Z = Standard error of the mean

e = Limit of tolerable error (or level of significance)

$$N = 1263$$

$$p = .5$$

$$q = (1 - .5) = .5$$

$$Z = 95 \text{ percent} = 1.96$$

$$e = 0.05 \text{ percent}$$

$$= \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 1263 \times .5 \times .5}{1263(0.05)^2 + (1.96)^2 \times .5 \times .5}$$

$$3.8416 \times 1263 \times .25$$

$$\frac{3.1575 + 3.9416 \times .25}{\frac{1212.985}{3.1575 + .96}} = \frac{1212.985}{4.1175} = 294.592 \approx \underline{295}$$

3.6 Method of Data Collection

The Questionnaire was used for data collection. The secondary data were collected from firms, journals, publication, textbooks and the internet. Ten questions (10) in the questionnaire were ranged.

3.7 Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was given to two experts from the industry and academia to measure face and content validity. To make sure that the research instruments applied in the work are valid, the research ensured that the instrument measure the concept they are supposed to measure.

3.8 Reliability of the Research Instrument

Internal consistency test was used to test the reliability of the instrument. This was done by administering 20 copies of the prepared questionnaire to the sample of the study. Cronbach's Alpha was used in determining the extent of consistency of the reliability.

A Cronbach's alpha value (∞) of greater 0.870 indicated very strong reliability.

Scale: All Variables

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	10	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	10	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.87	10

Scale reliabilities were calculated using Cronbach's Alpha; the result obtained was 0.87. This shows that the internal consistency of the scale is good for the purpose of this study because it is greater than 0.87 which was good.

3.9 Method of Data Analyses

Data from the questionnaire were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, percentages. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point Likert scale questions, the strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A) Neutral (N) Disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). Z- Test statistics was adopted in the test of hypotheses.

Data Presentation Analyses and Interpretation

4.1 Distribution and returned Questionnaire

4.1.1 Depicts the Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire

Table 4.1.1 Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire

	No Distributed	No Returned	Percent returned	No. not Returned	Percent not Returned
1 SMEs	295	255	86	40	14
Total	295	255	86%	40	14%

Source: From the questionnaire administration, 2024

Two hundred and ninety five (295) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents and two hundred and fifty five(255) copies were returned representing eighty six (86%) percent, while forty (40) copies of the questionnaire were not returned representing fourteen percent (14%). This shows a high rate of the respondents.

4.2 Data Relating to Research questions

4.2.1 The relationship between entrepreneurial creativity and revenue generation of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state

Table 4.2.1.1: Reveals the relationship between entrepreneurial creativity and revenue generation of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state

	5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1 Creativity helps develop new ways of improving an existing product and maintaining a competitive position	655 131 51.4	80 20 7.8	123 41 16.1	74 37 14.5	26 26 10.2	958 255 100%	3.76	1.457	Agree
2 Creativity helps to improve service and optimize the business growth	670 134 52.5	80 20 7.8	117 39 15.3	52 26 13.7	27 27 10.6	946 255 100%	3.71	1.463	Agree
3 Creativity allows entrepreneurs to think outside the box and expand their operations	540 108 42.4	80 20 7.8	201 67 26.3	50 25 9.8	35 35 13.7	906 255 100%	3.55	1.457	Agree
4 To view and solve problems more openly are enhanced with Creativity that helps to attract and retain customers	605 121 47.5	196 49 19.2	99 33 12.9	46 23 9.0	29 29 11.4	975 255 100%	3.82	1.402	Agree

Promoting creativity in the organisation help enhance customer experiences	745 149 57.4	148 37 18.0	66 22 8.6	52 26 7.8	21 21 8.2	1032 255 100%	4.05	1.351	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation							3.792	1.426	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.2.1.1, 151 respondents out of 2556 representing 59.2 percent agreed that Creativity helps develop new ways of improving an existing product and maintaining a competitive position with mean score 3.76 and standard deviation of 1.457. Creativity helps to improve service and optimize the business growth 154 respondents representing 60.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.71 and standard deviation of 1.463. Creativity allows entrepreneurs to think outside the box and expand their operations 128 respondents representing 50.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.55 and standard deviation of 1.457. To view and solve problems more openly are enhanced with Creativity that helps to attract and retain customers 170 respondents representing 66.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.82 and 1.351. Promoting creativity in the organisation help enhance customer experiences 186 respondents representing 75.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.05 and standard deviation 1.351.

4.2.2 The relationship between commitment and sales volume of small and medium enterprises in Enugu State

Table 4.2.2.1: Reveals the relationship between commitment and sales volume of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	The level of enthusiasm an entrepreneur put towards his/her tasks help drive business growth	550 110 43.1	240 60 23.5	54 18 7.1	86 43 16.9	24 24 9.4	954 255 100%	3.74	1.402	Agree
2	The feeling of responsibility that a entrepreneur has toward the goals of the business presents the opportunities for expansion	580 116 45.5	280 70 27.5	57 19 7.5	30 15 5.9	35 35 13.7	982 255 100%	3.85	1.409	Agree
3	Strong indicator of a self-discipline maximizes the lifetime value of the business	730 146 57.3	268 67 26.3	54 18 7.1	12 6 2.4	18 18 7.1	1082 255 100%	4.24	1.148	Agree
4	The level of resilience and persistence in the business attract new customers and retain existing ones	640 128 50.2	328 82 32.2	39 13 5.1	36 18 7.1	14 14 5.5	1057 255 100%	4.15	1.146	Agree
5	The entrepreneur hurdle difficulties to fulfill their	435 87	360 90	39 13	86 43	22 22	942 255	3.69	1.325	Agree

commitments not only to others but also to themselves and it help identify business health to a large extent

57.4 18.0 8.6 7.8 8.2 100%

Total Grand mean and standard deviation **3.934 1.286**

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.2.2.1, 170 respondents out of 255 representing 66.6 percent agreed that The level of enthusiasm an entrepreneur put towards his/her tasks help drive business growth with mean score 3.74 and standard deviation of 1.402. The feeling of responsibility that a entrepreneur has toward the goals of the business presents the opportunities for expansion 180 respondents representing 73.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation of 1.409. Strong indicator of a self-discipline maximizes the lifetime value of the business 213 respondents representing 83.6 percent agreed with mean score of 4.24 and standard deviation of 1.148. The level of resilience and persistence in the business attract new customers and retain existing ones 210 respondents representing 82.4 percent agreed with mean score of 4.15 and 1.146. The entrepreneur hurdle difficulties to fulfill their commitments not only to others but also to themselves and it help identify business health to a large extent 177 respondents representing 75.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.69 and standard deviation 1.325.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Hypothesis One: Entrepreneurial Creativity has relationship with the revenue generation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs)

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Creativity helps develop new ways of improving an existing product and maintaining a competitive position	Creativity helps to improve service and optimize the business growth	Creativity allows entrepreneurs to think outside the box and expand their operations	To view and solve problems more openly are enhanced with Creativity that helps to attract and retain customers	Promoting creativity in the organisation help enhance customer experiences
N	255	255	255	255	255
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.514	.525	.424	.475
	Negative	.102	.106	.137	.114
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	-.514	-.525	-.424	-.475	-.584
	8.204	8.391	6.763	7.577	9.331

Innovative Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business (IJEB)

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836-3960

Impact Factor: 9.68

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJEB/index>,

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
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a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $6.391 < 9.331$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that Entrepreneurial Creativity had significant positive relationship with the revenue generation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $6.391 < 9.331$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that entrepreneurial Creativity had significant positive relationship with the revenue generation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

4.3.2 Hypothesis Two: Entrepreneurial Commitment has relationship with the sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	The level of enthusiasm an entrepreneur put towards his/her tasks help drive business growth	The feeling of responsibility that a entrepreneur has toward the goals of the business presents the opportunities for expansion	Strong indicator of a self-discipline maximizes the lifetime value of the business	The level of resilience and persistence in the business attract new customers and retain existing ones	The entrepreneur hurdle difficulties to fulfill their commitments not only to others but also to themselves and it help identify business health to a large extent	
N	255	255	255	255	255	
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	
	Absolute	.431	.479	.585	.574	.444
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.094	.137	.071	.055	.086
	Negative	-.431	-.479	-.585	-.574	-.444
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	6.888	7.656	9.346	9.159	7.092	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $6.888 < 9.159$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that entrepreneurial Commitment had positive significant relationship with the Sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $6.888 < 9.159$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Entrepreneurial Commitment had positive significant relationship with the sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Entrepreneurial Creativity had significant positive relationship with the revenue generation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs)

From the result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z- value of $6.391 < 9.331$ against the critical Z- value of .000, which implies that entrepreneurial Creativity had significant positive relationship with the revenue generation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). In the support of the result in the literature review, Samuel & Samuel (2022) conducted a study on the effect of risk taking on market share of selected SMEs in Ado-odo/Ota, Ogun state. According to the findings, more than half of the SMEs (115, 77.2 %) have only been in business for less than five years and are predominantly (52, 34.9%) in the age range 33-37. The data also demonstrate that there is a link between taking risks and a small business's market share. The R-value was 0.58, indicating that the risk indicators used in the study explained 58 % of the variation in the outcome variable. The F-statistic was 18.3; $P=0.000$, according to the ANOVA table. Orga, Aniezue, Unaogu, Emehelu, Ugwa & Udeagha (2023) conducted a study on the relationship between Entrepreneurship education and Performance of the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Enugu State. The findings indicated that training workshops had direct positive relationship with problem solving skills, $r(95, n = 282) = .484 < .782, p < 0.05.$; mentorship had direct positive relationship with the reduction of unemployment $r(95, n = 282) = .511 < .730, p < 0.05.$ And opportunity evaluation had direct positive relationship with the number of business startups by SMEs in Enugu State, Nigeria $r(95, n = 282) = .515 < .760, p < 0.05.$

4.4.2 Commitment had positive significant relationship with the sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

From the result of hypothesis two, the calculated Z- value of $6.888 < 9.159$ against the critical Z- value of .000, which implies that Commitment had positive significant relationship with the sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). In the support of the result in the literature review, Ugwu (2021) conducted a study on the “effect of communication on service delivery of Enugu State fire service commission. The study revealed communication channels used in Enugu state fire service

commission, and also it examined how effective these communication channels are, and the impediments of communication flow in Enugu state fire service. Okojie, Enudu and Ile (2023) conducted a study on the effectiveness of social media in developing businesses in Enugu state. The findings indicated that the level of effectiveness of Facebook on the sales ($7.598 < 9.372$, $< p.05$). The level of effectiveness of Twitter on business expansion ($6.002 < 7.539$, $< p.05$) and the level of effectiveness of Instagram on the marketing of businesses in Enugu state is significantly high, ($6.771 < 8.781$, $< p.05$). The study concluded that Facebook, Twitter and Instagram had significant positive effectiveness on sales of businesses, business expansion and marketing of businesses in Enugu state and worldwide.

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Summary of Findings

- i. Entrepreneurial Creativity had significant positive relationship with the revenue generation of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), $Z(95, n = 255)$, $6.391 < 9.331$, $P. < .05$
- ii. Entrepreneurial **Commitment** had positive significant relationship with the sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), $Z(95, n = 255)$, $6.888 < 9.159$, $P. < .05$

5.2 Conclusions

The study concluded that Entrepreneurial Creativity and commitment had significant positive relationship with the revenue generation and Sales volume of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Passion helps to set a solid foundation for business and establish core values. Passion gives you the motivation and confidence that is needed to deliver the mission and purpose for what you do and why you do it. Entrepreneurship passion enables new markets to develop in the form of goods, services, and technology. It paves ways of generating wealth; these higher earnings contribute to increased national income and tax revenues. It promotes innovation, self-reliance and generates employment opportunities.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendation were made

- i. The management of the small and medium enterprises should be encouraged to be creative to help builds confidence and teach valuable life skills, including cognitive, physical and social emotional skills.
- ii. For effective making roles, responsibilities, and relationships there is need for commitment which gives everyone the opportunities for information they Need to do their jobs and to understand their contributions to the organisation. Effective commitment reduces the cost associated with conflicts, misunderstandings, and mistakes.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

Innovative Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business (IJEB)

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836-3960

Impact Factor: 9.68

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/IJEB/index>,

Email: contact@americaserial.com

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The studies done were carried outside entrepreneurial passion and performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the Entrepreneurial Creativity and revenue generation, Entrepreneurial commitment and Sales volume of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the entrepreneurial passion and performance of small and medium enterprises in Enugu state. The models contributes to the knowledge gap.

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Innovative Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business (IJEB)

Volume 13 Issue 1, January-March 2025

ISSN: 2836-3960

Impact Factor: 9.68

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